

Active Principle of *Myrsine Africana*, Linn.

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During a search for indigenous drugs, reputed to be of value as anthelmintics, the chemistry of the active constituents of *Myrsine africana* was studied. It is a small, evergreen, pubescent shrub known as *bebrang* in Hindi, belonging to the same family as *Embelia ribes* (N. O. *Myrsinacea*) but botanically quite distinct. In local bazaars, no such distinction is made between the berries of the two species and both of them are called by the same name, although *M. africana* is less commonly known and its berries are much smaller in size than that of *E. ribes*. The berries are used in Ayurvedic system of medicine as anthelmintic, especially in cases of tape worm and are also used in preparation of ointments for ringworm and other skin diseases. For our investigation authentic berries were collected through the forest officers of the Chakrata division (U. P.)

The dried berries on extraction with various organic solvents gave a crystalline material of golden colour which was identified as embelic acid through preparation and identification of its many derivatives (Kaul, Ray and Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 577; Hasan and Stedmann, *ibid.*, 1931, 2112). The berries when extracted with rectified spirit deposited along with the colouring matter, a white crystalline material which has been identified as quercitol. The presence of quercitol in *E. ribes* has not been reported by previous workers.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The dried and finely powdered berries were soaked in petroleum ether for 48 hours to remove the fatty ingredients, after which it was filtered under pressure and spread out in the sun to dry. This on extraction, in a Soxhlet, with chloroform deposited golden coloured crystalline plates (yield 3 %). These were removed and crystallised from rectified spirit in golden yellow plates, m.p. 143-44°. It gave a diacetyl derivative (m. p. 54°), a dibenzoyl derivative (m. p. 95-96°), dianilino derivative (m. p. 160-62°) and dioxime (m.p. 276°), which

have been found identical with the corresponding derivatives obtained from embelic acid.

The residue left over after extraction of embelic acid, was further extracted with rectified spirit. The alcoholic extract on concentration and standing deposited a brown mass of crystals which on separation were boiled with chloroform. This treatment removed the colouring matter and left a white crystalline residue which on crystallisation from water and purification gave colourless prisms, m. p. 228-30° (yield 1%). (Found: C, 44.0; H, 7.7 per cent).

This crystalline substance is practically insoluble in most of the organic solvents but dissolves readily in hot water. It has a slightly sweetish taste and is neutral in reaction; does not form precipitate with lead acetate and has an optical rotation of $[\alpha]_D = +24^\circ$ in water. On oxidation with manganese dioxide in acid solution it gives off acrid smell reminding of benzoquinone. It gives an amorphous pentaacetyl derivative. These properties and reactions establish the crystalline product to be quercitol.*

The berries of *E. ribes* were also examined and quercitol was isolated and identified. The presence of *d*-quercitol in *Myrsine africana* and *E. ribes* is nothing surprising since it has been found in several other plants namely in *Fragaceae*, *Menispermaceae*, *Myrtaceae*, *Sapotaceae*, *Loganiaceae* and others.

*There was not enough material to isolate and identify the products of permanganate oxidation (Kilian and Schafer, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 1762). Attempt was not made to collect more material to do this because analysis, m.p., rotation and other properties all tended to show that it was *d*-quercitol. Muller (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 1766) has established the identity of quercitol, isolated from the leaves of *Chamaecrops humilis* on similar evidence.